

Antibody Characterization Report for Rab-1A and Rab-1B

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Rab-1A and Rab-1B

Gene name: *RAB1A and RAB1B*

Uniprot: P62820 (Rab-1A) and Q9H0U4 (Rab-1B)

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized seven Rab-1A and five Rab-1B commercial antibodies for Western Blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. HAP1 *RAB1A and RAB1B* KO lines are available at Horizon discovery and were used in this study. Expression of Rab-1A and Rab-1B proteins in HAP1 is adequate as determined through DepMap [3, 4].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC007227c012	CVCL_B5KT	HAP1	<i>RAB1A</i> KO
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC001225c011	CVCL_TI00	HAP1	<i>RAB1B</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Rab-1A and Rab-1B antibodies tested

Intended Rab-1 target	Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Rab-1A	Abcam	ab302545**	GR3458765-3	AB_2942108	recombinant-mono	EPR27169-83	rabbit	0.502	Wb,IP,IF
Rab-1A	Bio-Techne	NBP3-11042*	MR288278	AB_2942092	monoclonal	7H4	mouse	1.000	Wb,IP
Rab-1A	Bio-Techne	NBP3-11043*	MR488278	AB_2942109	monoclonal	4G10	mouse	1.000	Wb,IP
Rab-1A	Cell Signaling Technology	13075**	1	AB_2665537	recombinant-mono	D3X9S	rabbit	0.200	Wb,IF
Rab-1A	Proteintech	11671-1-AP	66720	AB_2173437	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.700	Wb,IP,IF
Rab-1A	Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-44578	YA3805788	AB_2608352	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.500	Wb
Rab-1A	Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-104066	YA3806218A	AB_2853395	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb
Rab-1B	Bio-Techne	NBP3-18251	PR285216	AB_2942110	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb,IF
Rab-1B	Proteintech	17824-1-AP	39221	AB_2237881	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.200	Wb,IF
Rab-1B	Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-31880*	YA3806197	AB_2787503	monoclonal	7A12G2	mouse	1.000	Wb
Rab-1B	Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-104067	YA3806219A	AB_2853396	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb,IF
Rab-1B	Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-77240	YA3805998	AB_2720967	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb,IF

Wb=Western Blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody, n/a=not available

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the Rab-1A and Rab-1B antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21429 and A21424).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by Western Blot

Western Blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. HAP1 WT, *RAB1A* and *RAB1B* KO (listed in Table 1) were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western Blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western Blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual Western Blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL

Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with or the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody or 10 µl of NBP3-18251 (unknown concentration) to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and Western Blot precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Prot-A:HRP (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8651) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.3 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. HAP1 WT and *RAB1A* or HAP1 WT and *RAB1B* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary Rab-1A and Rab-1B antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

A. Rab1A

B. Rab1B

Figure 1: Rab-1A and Rab1-B antibody screening by Western Blot

A. Rab1A

B. Rab1B

Figure 2: Rab-1A and Rab1-B antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

A. Rab1A

B. Rab1B

Figure 3: Rab-1A and Rab1-B antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 1: Rab-1A and Rab-1B antibody screening by Western Blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *RAB1A* and *RAB1B* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for Western Blot with the indicated Rab-1A (**A**) and Rab-1B (**B**) antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab302545** at 1/200, NBP3-11042* at 1/500, NBP3-11043* at 1/500, 13075** at 1/200, 11671-1-AP at 1/500, PA5-44578 at 1/500, PA5-104066 at 1/500, NBP3-18251 at 1/200, 17824-1-AP at 1/500, MA5-31880* at 1/500, PA5-104067 at 1/200, PA5-77240 at 1/200. Predicted band size: 22 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Rab-1A and Rab-1B antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated Rab-1A (**A**) and Rab-1B (**B**) antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for Western Blot. For Rab-1A Western Blot (**A**), ab302545** was used at 1/200. For Rab-1B Western Blot (**B**), 17824-1-AP was used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; LC= antibody light chain. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: Rab-1A and Rab-1B antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *RAB1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and *Rab1A* KO (**A**) or *Rab1B* KO (**B**) cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated Rab-1A (**A**) and Rab-1B (**B**) antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody dilution used: ab302545** at 1/100, NBP3-11042* at 1/100, NBP3-11043* at 1/100, 13075** at 1/800, 11671-1-AP at 1/700, PA5-44578 at 1/500, PA5-104066 at 1/100, NBP3-18251 at 1/100, 17824-1-AP at 1/50, MA5-31880* at 1/1000, PA5-104067 at 1/1000, PA5-77240 at 1/50. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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